

DISTANCE TRAINING OF PERSONNEL AND ITS ADVANTAGES

¹Kienya Elena Alexandrovna, ²Bodrova Ella Mikhailovna

¹Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

²Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Belarusian State Economic University

г. Minsk, Republic of Belarus

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Abstract. The article considers programs, services and applications for distance learning. Advantages and calculations on the effectiveness of this form of personnel training are presented.

Keywords: distance learning, courses, personnel, programs, applications.

ДИСТАНЦИОННОЕ ОБУЧЕНИЕ ПЕРСОНАЛА И ЕГО ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА

¹Киеня Елена Александровна, ²Бодрова Элла Михайловна

¹канд. экон. наук, доцент

²канд. экон. наук, доцент

Белорусский государственный экономический университет

г. Минск, Республика Беларусь

Аннотация. В статье рассмотрены программы, сервисы и приложения для дистанционного обучения. Представлены преимущества и расчеты по эффективности данной формы обучения персонала.

Ключевые слова: дистанционное обучение, курсы, персонал, программы, приложения.

XODIMLARNI MASOFAVIY O'QITISH VA UNING AFZALLIKLARI

¹Kienya Elena Aleksandrovna, ²Bodrova Ella Mixaylovna,

¹t.f.n. ekon. fanlari, dotsent

²t.f.n. ekon. fanlari, dotsent

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Izoh. Maqolada masofaviy ta'lim uchun dasturlar, xizmatlar va ilovalar muhokama qilinadi. Kadrlar tayyorlashning ushbu shaklining afzalliklari va samaradorligining hisob-kitoblari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: masofaviy ta'lim, kurslar, xodimlar, dasturlar, ilovalar.

The essence of distance learning is to train personnel using free services for distance learning and not to spend a significant amount of money on travel and accommodation. Distance learning is cheaper than conventional training not only by reducing the cost of travel and accommodation in another city, but also by the amount of expenses on the organization of the courses themselves. According to average calculations, distance learning is 50-60% cheaper than face-to-face training.

Distance learning system allows you to acquire the necessary skills and new knowledge with the help of a personal computer and access to the Internet. The location of the computer does not matter, so you can study at home, at work, in a distance learning center, as well as in any other place where there is the necessary equipment with Internet access.

There are many different programs and services for this method of learning, on the basis of which it is convenient to conduct classes and control the knowledge gained. Сервисы, с помощью которых можно проводить обучение:

1 Moodle. Today Moodle is undoubtedly one of the most popular distance learning systems. The service offers the user a variety of dashboards, the ability to track the progress of learners and multimedia support. The system allows you to create courses adapted for cell phones and computers.

Also, the service gives you the opportunity to earn money on your courses, as it has integration with the payment system PayPal, which makes it easy and understandable to pay for orders.

Another important advantage of Moodle is its user community. Unlike other distance learning systems, here you can almost instantly get answers to most of your questions by contacting the online technical support base.

2 Yo - stadia. Yo - stadium - an electronic educational environment, to start working in which, you just need to register on the site and create a personal space for your company, which will be placed training materials and tasks for students.

The functionality of this service is more oriented towards practical work. Yo-stadi, of course, allows publishing educational materials, but most of the system is designed for all kinds of knowledge assessment and testing.

The service contains a sufficient number of tools for organizing training and testing:

- "workspace", where course training materials, announcements and assignments are published, the workspace is created by the instructor (manager) for training and can unite several groups and courses. Trainees access the workspace by request.

- "test", Yo-stadi has a powerful functionality for testing. The test can be created on the site, or imported from a document, pre-formatted in accordance with special rules. A detailed report on the answers of each test taker is available. There is a possibility to limit the terms, the ability to switch between browser windows.

- "file" implies the possibility of uploading files that the teacher can evaluate and comment on.

In general, Yo-stadi deserves an excellent rating and is a good solution for organizations wishing to organize staff training without any costs for purchasing distance learning systems. 3 ATutor. Эта система дистанционного обучения имеет множество полезных функций: от email-уведомлений до файлового хранилища.

One of the most striking advantages of ATutor is its client-oriented and easy and pleasant interface, which makes this system an ideal tool for those who are just beginning to explore the world of e-learning.

ATutor also offers a number of pre-installed themes to speed up the course creation process. And it is impossible not to mention the various evaluation tools, file backup, statistics and the possibility of integrating surveys.

4 Eliademy offers catalogs of distance learning courses, assessment tools and even a mobile application for the Android operating system.

Distance learning coordinators can easily and simply upload courses and send invitations for students to their email addresses.

5 Forma LMS. From analyzing the overall level of knowledge to detailed statistics and reporting, Forma LMS boasts a rather extensive set of available functions.

The service also has various certifications, competent management support, and a wide range of tools for virtual classroom management, including various calendars and event managers.

This system is ideal for corporate training programs and offers access to an active online community where each user can find many useful tips on how to get the most out of this service.

6 Microsoft Teams Meeting is a collaboration application, an alternative to Zoom, that allows you and your group to gain new knowledge, organize information, and always stay connected.

This program has a place to store files for work, which means it automatically includes access to 1 terabyte of cloud storage. All documents, files will be automatically saved in the cloud.

To start working with the service you need to follow the link in the application and the document legibly explains the purpose of each button and gives tips on organizing the learning process. In addition, there is a training video on working with Microsoft Teams Meeting and auxiliary applications in English and Russian.

Another plus of this application is the ability to quickly organize an online meeting. Video conferences are available in other services of distance learning systems, but in Microsoft Teams Meeting they are easy to schedule through the calendar, set up a notification within the platform or by mail, and to quickly connect the right person, you just need to mention his name through the dog (@). It's convenient to hand out tasks, conduct testing, and even share information from your screen (screen demo).

An important feature is the automatic checking of tests and other assignments.

This is only a small part of those services that are available for remote training of personnel. There are a huge number of them and the main advantage of these services is that they are free and the company does not have to overpay money for the program.

The main advantage of distance learning over the form of individual training, which is used at the enterprise at the moment, with distance learning system, you can realize mass training of trainees with a small staff of teachers.

The use of distance learning system allows to create courses to improve the potential of specialists working at the enterprise, to create a certification center, where by means of control tasks and tests it is possible to adequately and objectively check the level of professional suitability of employees.

As an assessment of the cost-effectiveness of distance learning, the calculation of the effectiveness of distance learning is given.

To determine the choice of the form of training can be determined by the formula:

$$E = (RO \times KO) - (RD \times KD), \quad (1)$$

where RD and RO - training costs per employee for distance and in-person training;

KO and KD - the number of employees studying by distance and face-to-face training.

Assuming that face-to-face training for one specialist on courses is 365 rubles, and the cost of one hour of lecturer's work is 20 rubles. The organization sends 10 specialists for ten days of training for five hours a day.

Calculation of the costs of full-time training:

- 1) training of 10 specialists - 3,650 rubles.
- 2) to a lecturer for 50 hours of training - 1,000 r.

The organization would pay 3,650 rubles for a face-to-face course, and if we use a distance learning system for the same course, we could train more specialists, and the organization would only have to pay the lecturer for lecturing.

If even an hour of lectures will cost 36 rubles, we get the following:

$$E = (RO \times KO) - (RD \times KD) = 3,650 - 1,000 = 2,650 \text{ rubles.}$$

Also, let's consider the variant of advanced training of specialists of HR department in number of 5 persons, on the basis of the State educational institution "Institute of advanced training and retraining of managers and specialists of industry "Personnel Industry" of the Republic of Belarus, Minsk.

To begin with, let's consider the costs of training using the full-time format of training.

The table shows the cost of training per specialist, including the cost of courses, accommodation and travel.

Table 1 - Cost of training in full-time format per person

Name of direction	Training schedule	Cost of courses, p.	Cost of accommodation (single room), p.	Cost of travel (two-way), p.	Total, p.
Modern forms of improving HR management processes	25.09.2023 – 30.09.2023	380	300	40	720

Next, we calculate the costs for all five HR specialists. Knowing the cost of training, accommodation and travel, it is possible to calculate the costs of staff development that the company will incur in the case of full-time training for each employee.

The cost of full-time training for five specialists of the HR department = 380 (the cost of courses for one person) × 5 (the number of specialists who go to training) + 75 (cost of accommodation for one person in a single room) × 5 × 4 (number of days of accommodation) + 20 (cost of travel from Rechitsa to Minsk for one person) × 5 × 20 (return trip) = 3 600 p.

And now let's calculate how much money will be needed to train five HR specialists using distance learning. The training is conducted using the free Moodle service, as it is the most convenient and practical program for distance learning, which can be accessed both from a computer and from a phone.

The course will consist of lectures, assignments, webinars, seminars, tests, surveys. The lectures will provide theoretical material on the course. A lecture can be any text document, presentation, video clip, and the like. Assignments allow the instructor to set a task that requires

students to prepare a detailed answer. Typical assignments are cases, tasks. This element allows the instructor to write feedback and grade the answers. Webinars will be used to provide training in a video conference format to improve the interaction between the trainees and the instructor. In the workshop, the learning process takes place to organize training on the desired topic with mutual evaluation and self-assessment on a set of defined criteria. And at the end, to check the learned material there are tests and surveys to assess how useful the training was, how well the material was learned. Also, tests and surveys are conducted at the beginning of the course to identify some gaps in the existing knowledge, if any, and to work through them.

The cost of the course remains unchanged, but there is no need to allocate funds for travel and accommodation. Based on this we get the following:

The cost of training using distance learning for five specialists of the personnel department = 380 (the cost of courses for one person) × 5 (the number of specialists who will be trained) = 1 900 p.

The result of the calculations is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 - Costs of training using face-to-face and distance forms of professional development

Name of department	Number of trained people		Training costs, p.		Savings, p.
	full-time education	distance learning	full-time education	distance learning	
Human Resources	5	5	3 600	1 900	1 700

Thus, the application of distance training would reduce the cost of employee training by 1,700 p., or 52.7%.

Application of distance learning allows to train a much larger number of employees. As a result of the above factors, the human resources potential of the organization as a whole increases and this determines the successful development of the enterprise.

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